

THE ROLE OF DENIAL AND AFFIRMATION IN LITERARY TEXTS

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Abstract: It is known that sentences are in the form of affirmation or negation is formed. The category of affirmation and negation is also in logic, is also studied in grammar. All this is language and because of the unity of thought, attitude. Logical negation appears in sentence form, and grammatical negation appears in sentence form. This article discusses the role of affirmative negation in literary texts.

Key words: denial meaning, affirmative meaning, rhetorical question, formal-grammatical , prosodic tools.

INTRADUCTION

As a result of his life experiences and observations, people understand the events that occur in society and nature, learns the rules. A reflection in a person's mind opinions collected on the basis of life experiences are conclusions and are phenomena specific to the logical category of a negative nature. A negative (unrealized) thought becomes real after being positive. In other words, a negative opinion is known only to the speaker and unknown to the listener, and it is positive, after the situation, it becomes clear to the listener. Positive thought is realized in language through speech.

MAIN PART

The category of negation is common to all languages, and its expression differs by peculiarities does. Accordingly, the category of negation is in every language is considered a separate problem. Some about the negation category in Uzbek things are done. These works are grammatical features of negation such as expression and dialectal character issues. Negation is usually expressed with or without the use of language. Accordingly, the category of negation is linguistic and discursive it will be appropriate to check the plan. Logical affirmative and negative categories are among the most characteristic features of reporting in a sentence. The main point one of the signs of judgment is the way of confirmation or denial is formed with Affirmation and denial exist not only between thoughts, but also between concepts. In other words, affirmation and negation are reflected both in the context of the sentence and in the semantics of the word. But negation specific to the concept does not cause mental negation in the sentence, does not affect the affirmative content of the sentence. Even pairs (antonyms) forming a negation relationship when each becomes part of separate sentences both statements are affirmative (one is affirmative, one is not negative). This suit is big on you - confirmation mean, this suit is too small for you - confirmation mean.

Accordingly, the relation of affirmation and negation specific to the sentence should not be confused with the antonymic relationship between concepts. The negative category is participle in the sentence is formed through Its manifestation in the clause is characteristic of the whole sentence, and its expression in other clauses is unique to that piece. That is, the part of the sentence is negative if it is in the form, the sentence itself is in the negative content, negative forms in other parts of the sentence does not affect the content of the confirmation. Negation in cut is general, and the negation in other clauses is particular. Let's compare: It is not expected to rain tomorrow (affirmative sentence)— It is not expected to rain tomorrow (negative sentence).

Sentence-specific negatives usually follow affirmative sentences produced using linguistic or non-linguistic means. Linguistic means of negation means the formal-grammatical, lexical- it is understood to be expressed using grammatical and prosodic means. In Uzbek, there are not many formal-grammatical means of negation, only one (-ma). But its scope of application is very wide.

In rhetorical interrogative sentences, a strong affirmative meaning through the negative form of the sentence, as opposed to affirmative forms strong negative meanings are expressed through . Such mental state of the speaker or other person in the sentences is portrayed with extreme poignancy.

In addition to negative expressions, one more there are also a number of speech devices through which actions, objects, signs, etc. are strictly denied. Language units are involved in such usage, of course. But in such a place speech is of special importance. In speech, any statement in the form of an affirmation is a negation and vice versa affirmative statements. At the same time, it can express expressiveness. In this case the listener's mood and attitude towards the interlocutor depends on the situation and context.

Under certain conditions, using intonation, sentences in the negative form can express the meaning of affirmation, while sentences in the affirmative form can express the meaning of negation. At such a time, expressiveness is always strong.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

So, the following can be pointed out as important expressions showing the relationship of form and meaning in affirmative and negative sentences:

1. Affirmative and negative forms always have expressiveness if they express the opposite (opposite) meaning, or rather, the affirmative form to express expressiveness affirmative instead of negation or conversely negative form forms are used.

2. If the negative form is used twice in the sentence, two different situations are observed:

1) if the second negation (in order) is the first If negation negates, the meaning of affirmation follows and this meaning is reinforced. In an affirmation expressed by the negation of a negation, the meaning is more impressive than in a simple affirmation;

2) if the next negation is not related to the first negation, the sentence remains in the meaning of negation. In this case, there is no negation of the negation;

3) the negative in the clause is common to the sentence, other the negation in the passage is often of a specific character. The negative form in the specific clause causes the sentence to be in the negative sense, in other clauses negation does not affect the content of the sentence.

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